

ISSN: 3026-8370

GAMJI

JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY LEGAL STUDIES

VOL 1 - ISSUE 1 | JAN - JUN, 2024

A PUBLICATION OF

GAMJI INSTITUTE FOR TRAINING
AND RESEARCH

GAMJI

JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY LEGAL STUDIES

VOL 1, ISSUE 1

JANUARY – JUNE, 2024

ISSN 3026-8370

**A PUBLICATION OF
GAMJI INSTITUTE FOR TRAINING AND RESEARCH
BAUCHI STATE,
NIGERIA
07068297660
support@gamjiinstitute.org**

**This Journal can be cited as:
Gamji Journal of Contemporary Legal Studies, 1(1)
ISSN:3026-8370, 2024**

EDITORIAL BOARD

1. TURKI ALGOERE, PhD - **EDITOR-IN-CHIEF**

University of Business and Technology, Jeddah, Saudi Arabia

2. RAO QASIM IDREES, PhD

Associate Professor of Law/

Chairperson, International Trade and Investment Laws,

School of Law, University of Gujrat, Pakistan

3. PROF. UMAR ALKALI

Faculty of Law,

University of Maiduguri, Nigeria

4. SULAIMAN SANTURAKI, PhD

Nigerian Law School, Yola Campus, Nigeria

5. PROF. MUBARAK T. ADEKILEKUN

University of Ilorin, Nigeria

6. GRACE EMMANUEL KAKA, PhD

Bauchi State University, Gadau, Nigeria

CONTENTS

COPYRIGHT ACT OF NIGERIA, 2023: AN APPRAISAL OF RIGHTS Ibrahim Danjuma_____	1
APPRAISAL OF THE CHALLENGES AND THE PROSPECT OF PROSECUTING CYBERCRIME IN NIGERIA Aminu Umar_____	21
A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS ON <i>SAHIFAT AL-MADINA</i> AND THE PRINCIPLES OF A MODERN CONSTITUTION VIS-À-VIS THE POSITION OF POLITICS UNDER ISLAMIC LAW Babayo Yakubu, Haruna Alhaji Garba, Waheedah Yunusa Muhammad_____	41
THE SCIENCE OF JUDICIAL PRECEDENTS AND THE CHAMELEONIC NATURE OF JUDICIAL DECISIONS IN POLITICAL MATTERS IN NIGERIA Antom Vanen Lawrence_____	58
AN EXAMINATION OF THE JURISDICTION AND COMPETENCE OF THE FEDERAL AND STATES HIGH COURTS OVER ISLAMIC BANKING DISPUTES IN NIGERIA Ibrahim Buhari Shehu_____	73
AN ASSESSMENT ON THE ADEQUACY OF PERSONAL INCOME TAX ACT IN NIGERIA Ahmad Aliyu_____	93
AN APPRAISAL OF THE APPLICATION OF THE AFRICAN CHARTER ON DEMOCRACY, ELECTIONS AND GOVERNANCE IN NIGERIA Usman Sani, Salisu Abubakar_____	106
THE NIGERIAN JUVENILE JUSTICE SYSTEM: IMPLEMENTATION, CHALLENGES AND THE WAY FORWARD Aminu Umar_____	128
AN APPRAISAL OF THE TREATMENT AND CARE OF GUNSHOT VICTIMS ACT, 2017 Agbo Friday Ojonugwa, Mary Arthur-Jolasinmi_____	152

A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS ON SAHIFAT AL-MADINA AND THE PRINCIPLES OF A MODERN CONSTITUTION VIS-À-VIS THE POSITION OF POLITICS UNDER ISLAMIC LAW

By

Babayo Yakubu*, Haruna Alhaji Garba, Waheedah Yunusa Muhammad*****

*Lecturer I, Department of Islamic Law, Bauchi State University Gadau.

G.S.M. +2348039647387 Email: yakubumisau1031@gmail.com

**Lecturer I, Department of Islamic Law, Bauchi State University Gadau.

G.S.M. +2348037405179 Email: agharunakm@gmail.com

Waheedah Yunusa Muhammad

***Lecturer II, Department of Islamic Law, Bauchi State University Gadau.

G.S.M. +2348066227630 Email: Yunusawaheedah@gmail.com

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13126501

ABSTRACT

Many countries of the modern world are guided by a single document referred to as a constitution. Those without a single document as a Constitution still claimed to have an unwritten one. Thus, Countries without a Constitution are frowned at and regarded as undemocratic and Countries that are inclining towards Islamic law are viewed as having a system that is not compatible with Democracy. Some writers even went as far as claiming that Islam has nothing to do with politics and that there is no any element of politics in Islam. To them, Madina was never a State and Sahifat al-Madina was not a constitution, but a mere document of agreement.¹ This article seeks to answer the questions as to whether politics is part of Islam or not and whether Sahifat al-Madina was really a constitution or a mere document of agreement. All these will be done through content analysis of some Qur'anic verses as well as the Hadith of the Prophet and analyzing the modern constitutional principles against the provision of Sahifat Al-Madina to see whether such principles were contained therein or not. In conclusion the findings in this study clearly shows that the message of Islam

1 Ali Abdulraziq, *Al-Islam Wal Usulul Hukum* (Islam and the Fundamentals of Government) (Cairo: Al-Hay'a 1993); J. S. Kirman, 'Islam, Politics and Governance (2008)' *Totalitarian Movements and Political Religions*, (9) (1) 43-59; L. Z. Munir, 'Islam and Politics' *International Seminar on Islam and Universal Values; Islam's Contribution to the Construction of a Pluralistic World*. Jakarta [2004] available @ <www.ifp.org.> Accessed on 14 June 2024; Souad T. Ali, *A Religion, Not A State*; Ali 'Abd al-Raziq's Islamic Justification of Political Secularism (Salt Lake City; The University of Utah Press, 2009); Mark Negner, *Islamic Government: The Medieval Sunni Islamic Theory of the Caliphate and the Debate over the revival of Caliphate in Egypt 1924-1926* (PhD Thesis; University of Chicago 2001) 193.

can only be sustained through political regime as such from the cited authorities, it is obvious that politics is part and parcel of Islam and Sahifat al-Madina was clearly a Constitution.

Keywords: Islam, Politics, Sahifat al-Madina, Constitution.

1. INTRODUCTION

The idea of separating politics from religion comes from the Bible; “Render to Christ what is Christ’s, render to Caesar what is Caesar’s”.² This simply means religion is for Christ and leadership (Politics) is for the Kingdom, hereby separating religion and Politics.³ Muslim political thinkers and writers are of different opinions on this topic. Some reject the idea of politics in Islam entirely while some accept the idea entirely and we have those claiming that Islam can only accommodate politics.⁴ It was an Egyptian scholar Ali Abdulrazi that brought such argument into the Muslims’ world.⁵ At the wake of the abolishment of Islamic Caliphate in 1926 in Turkey, he wrote a book titled *Al-Islam Wal Usul Al-Hukm* i.e., Islam and the Principles of Government; the book supported the abolishment of the Caliphate and declared that: **i.** Politics is not part of Islam **ii.** That the message of the Prophet has nothing to do with Politics, that the message of the Prophet did not have any element of Politics. **iii.** That the one who established the Islamic State in Madina was not the Prophet (S.A.W), it was Abu-Bakr (R.A). He cited Qur’anic verses and some Hadith to justify his claim. These three points in his book raise a lot of uproar in the Muslim world. The book was translated in almost all the major languages in Europe by the western world. The west supported the book. He uses verses from the Qur’an and Hadith to support his argument. “I sent you to bring good news and warning...” So, to him based on this verse there is no any element of Politics in his task, only glad tidings and warning. “I did not sent you as an agent” Here, as the Prophet is not an agent, then he did not have any power and without power he is not a political leader. There is no element of power and so no politics. “Remind, your duty is only to remind, it is not your duty to force”. He said from this verse, the duty of the prophet is just to remind people that if you do this you go to

2 Mathew 22, *New Testament*

3 Zaid Mohamad, *Principles of Government in Islam* (A Lecture Note Prepared for Graduate Students of Kulliyah of Laws, International Islamic University, Malaysia 2016)

4 Omar Ashour, ‘Democratic Islam? Assessing the Bases of Democracy in Islamic Political Thought’ (2008) Available @< www.mcgill.ca/mes >accessed on 22nd March, 2024.

5 Zaid Mohamad p.22

paradise or you go to hell, and the prophet should not force anyone as such he has no political power.⁶

Ali Abdulrazi cited some prophetic tradition to support his argument. “Take it easy, I am not a king, I am only a son of a Quraish woman who used to eat dried meat” So; according to Ali Abdulrazi the prophet is only a human and not a king. So the prophet denied having a political power and that means there is no element of politics in his leadership. In another hadith the Prophet said “You know better about your job (worldly affairs).” Here too, Ali Abdulrazi argued that the Prophet himself shows that his mission is not worldly affairs as the message of the Prophet has nothing to do with political power.

This article seeks to answer the questions as to whether politics is part of Islam or not and whether *Sahifat al-Madina* was really a constitution or a mere document of agreement. All these is done through content analysis of some Qur’anic verses as well as the Hadith of the Prophet and analyzing the modern constitutional principles against the provision of *Sahifat al-Madina* to see whether such principles were contained in *Sahifat Al-Madina* or not. This is achieved first by debunking the view of those authors that politics is not part of Islam and that *Sahifat al-Madina* was not a Constitution but a mere document of agreement, this will be done by analyzing the view of Ali Abdulrazi, providing authorities from Qur’an, Sunnah and Ijma on the elements of politics under Islamic Law then definition and features of *Sahifat al-Madina* is looked at as well principles of modern Constitution with comparative analysis bringing out the similarities of the modern constitutional principles from the content of *Sahifat al-Madina*. The findings of the study form the concluding part of the work.

2. ANALYSIS OF ALI ABDULRAZI’S VIEW

The analysis of the verses and the hadith quoted by Ali Abdulrazi was right, that the verses show no elements of politics in them. However, all the verses cited were revealed in *Makkah* and at that time the message of the Prophet was concerned with *Akidah*. However, in *Madina* a lot of verses on political system, economic system and social system were revealed.⁷ On the hadith cited by Ali Abdulrazi that the prophet (S.A.W.) himself said he is not a king, the scholars said he made his analysis out of context; the reality of the event was that the man was brought before the Prophet (S.A.W.) and the man was shivering due to fear as other kings at the time were known for cruelty. The Prophet calms him down by making that statement. As

⁶ James Broucek, *The Controversy of Shaykh ‘Ali ‘Abd Al-Raziq* (PhD Thesis Florida State University, 2012)

⁷ Zaid Mohamad 7

for the second hadith cited by Ali Abdulrazi which relates to the Prophet expressing his view on date's pollination which turns out to be unproductive and when the farmers complained to him, he said you know better your job. Here the scholars said that it was not proper for Abdulrazi to generalize the specific. If the Prophet (S.A.W.) does not know about Agriculture it does not mean he did not know about politics.⁸

3. ELEMENTS OF POLITICS IN THE QUR'AN

Allah says "There affairs are conducted by consultation" in another verse Allah commanded thus "Consult them in the matters" these verses emphasis the need for *shura* (consultation) which is a system of government in Islam that has to do with decision making. In *Shura*, consultation has to be made with the *Shura* committee in order to reach a decision. Unlike democracy, *Shura* does not always follow the majority. It is said the above two verses will apply in two different circumstances, the first verse "there affairs are conducted by consultation" applies where there is no existing leader, such as when Umar (R.A) was stabbed, before he died, he directed those who were promised paradise to make consultation among themselves to appoint a leader within three days.⁹ As for the second verse, its application should be by a leader, as the verse indicated the word "*Shawir hum*" i.e., "Consult them" is "*Mufrad*" (Singular) and so refers to the leader. The important thing here is that making decision is a political matter. Another verse provides; "Those who did not rule with what Allah has revealed are among the unbelievers" The word related to the discussion here is "*yahkum*" i.e., "Ruling" which is also a political activity. Another verse is "Rule between them with what Allah has revealed and do not follow their vain desire" all the verses relate to ruling, which is a political activity which shows that the Qur'an also deals with Politics. In another verse, Allah says: "Oh, you who believed, obey Allah, obey the messenger and those in authority among you". Here too the word "*Ulil amr*" i.e., "those charged with authority among you" is a political term. Also "*adi'ul*" i.e., "obey" relates to power, which is a political term.¹⁰

The above cited verses show clearly that there are verses containing the element of politics in the Qur'an which Ali Abdulrazi ignored.

4. PROVISION IN THE SUNNAH REGARDING POLITICS

8 ibid

9 Zaid Mohamad, 5.

10 ibid 7

The Prophet was reported to have said; “It is not permitted for three people to be in any part of the earth except they appointed one of them a leader” It is clear from this Hadith that leading as a political activity in Islam is obligatory. In another hadith the Prophet was reported to have said: “When you are three in a journey, you should appoint one of you a leader” the Prophet also said that; anyone who died and he had never paid *bay’ah* (to a leader) he died the death of *jahiliyyah* i.e., he died as a *kafir*. Here “allegiance to a leader” is a political term. The Prophet also said that “Listening and obeying is a duty as long as one is not commanded to commit *ma’asiyyah* (evil) and when one is commanded to commit *ma’asiyyah* there should not be listening or obeying”. Here too it is clear that “listening and obeying” the leader is a political activity.¹¹

5. IJMA OF THE COMPANION REGARDING POLITICS IN ISLAM

There are a lot of *ijma* (consensus) regarding politics in Islam. However, we will consider the appointment of Abubakar (R.A.) as an example in this regard. Before the Prophet passed away, he did not appoint any successor. After the Prophet dead, the *Muhajirun* and the *Ansar* gathered in a place called *Saqifah bani Sa’idah*, discussing who will succeed the Prophet. The discussion continues for three days and all the while the body of the Prophet was not buried. The companions knew that the Prophet was reported to have said three things should be done as soon as possible; i. debt should be repaid as soon as possible ii. Dead body should be washed and buried as soon as possible, and iii. Girl, when she shows desire to marry, she should be given in marriage as soon as possible. Despite the above hadith and in this case not an ordinary dead body but the body of the Prophet, this shows the importance of leadership in Islam, which is a political term.¹²

6. SAHIFAT AL-MADINA AND THE ESTABLISHMENT OF THE ISLAMIC STATE OF MADINA

Before the Prophet’s migration to Madina, there was no existing central authority or leadership in place in Madina. At the point of Prophet’s entry to Madina, the two tribes (*Aus* and *Khazraj*) that formed the majority of Madina population accepted Islam, including their leaders. Those members of such tribes that did not accepted Islam, respected the decision of their leaders and accepted the Prophet as a leader. The Jews of Madina were allies to the *Aus* and *Khazraj* tribe and therefore were obliged to respect the agreements of their confederates. From all these

11 *ibid* 9

12 Zaid Mohamed 10

arrangements, the *Aus* and *Khazraj*, the Muslim emigrants and the Jews living within the territory of the city of Madina under the leadership of the Prophet without any foreign powers, completed the requirements of a city-state.¹³ The name “*Al Madina*” literally means the “Stronghold or City” came to replace the original name of the place “*Yathrib*” and it gradually comes to be referred to as “*Madinatul Al-Nabi*” that is “The Stronghold or City of the Prophet”. It should always be remembered that the Prophet was first a religious leader before anything, as he derived his Political and judicial powers from such position. Therefore, shortly after he arrived in Madina, he immediately established a Mosque which became the headquarter of his State.¹⁴ The Prophet, in order to trace the social, religious and demographic composition of Madina and determine its physical boundaries, asked the companions to have a population census with the result showing that a total of 10,000 (Ten thousand people) were living in Madina. 1,500 were Muslims, 4000 were Jews and 4500 were polytheist Arabs. From this, the Prophet realised that Madina is a place of diversity and is composed of a pluralistic society. Therefore, he adopted a course of action accordingly to deal with the situation resourcefully. Thus, the Prophet drafted the Constitution of Madina (*Sahifat al-Madina*), which some writers find it parallel with the United States of America’s Constitution from its religious pluralism to its emphasis on justice and domestic tranquility¹⁵

7. DEFINITION OF SAHIFAT AL-MADINA

Muhammad Hamidullah was quoted commenting on the peculiarity of *Sahifat al-Madina* in the Constitutional History of the World writes; “Prophet Muhammad consulted his followers as well as his non-Muslims neighbours; they all assembled in the house of Anas and resolved to constitute themselves into a city-state. The constitutional law was drawn up in an act which fortunately has been integrally preserved for us. It was the constitution of first Muslim City-State. It was equally the first constitution ever written for a state in the history of the world.¹⁶

Sahifat al-Madina can be regarded as a document dealing with tribal affairs during the Prophet’s early migration to Madina and which formed the basis of a multi-religious state under his leadership.¹⁷

13 Hashim, Y.A. The Governmental System of the Prophet Muhammad: A Comparative Study in Constitutional Law” (Dar Al-Kotob Al-Ilmiyah Lebanon, 2011) (2) (42)

14 Hashim, Y A 51

15 Parvaze Ahmad Bhat, *Pluralism and Diversity in the Sirah Literature; A Study of the Contemporary Scholars on Prophet Muhammad (S.A.W.)* (PhD Thesis Islamic Studies Aligarh Muslim University India 2013) (124)

16 *ibid.*

17 Available @ www.en.wikipedia.com accessed on 9 July 2024

8. FEATURES OF SAHIFAT AL-MADINA

Although some regarded the document as a treaty to regulate between the Muslims emigrants, the people of Madina and the Jews, further scrutiny will reveal that the main features of a treaty is missing from *Sahifat Al-Madina* as there was no any reference to the names and signatures of the contracting parties as contained in the Prophet's other treaties.¹⁸ It is also clear from the text of the document that Prophet Muhammad alone promulgated the document as a Constitution for the Islamic State, to regulate the co-existence of the diverse people of Madina. From the content of the Constitution, the citizenry of the State included the Muslims from Makkah and Madina as well as the Madina pagans and the Jews whom were all referred to as one community (*Ummah*) even though the Muslims automatically occupied the leadership position. The document has two parts, from article 1 to article 24 was first drafted to govern the Muslims themselves; the *Muhajirun* and the *Ansar* and the other part of the document was to govern the Muslims, non-Muslim Arabs and the Jews. All the three groups, i.e., the Muslim Arabs, non-Muslim Arabs and the Jews were referred to as one *ummah* in the *Sahifat al-Madina*.¹⁹ The relationship was to be based on solidarity and brotherhood, helping out one another in any given situation. Religion was the first major consideration above any other relationship. They were one against any other outsider. They all pledged their allegiance to the Prophet and subjected themselves to the Laws enacted by the Prophet.²⁰

As for the existing tribes in Madina, the Constitution recognized the tribes as administrative units under the overall leadership of Prophet Muhammad. The Muslims from Makkah (emigrants) were considered as one tribe. The Constitution imposed duties on each tribe to maintain law and order as well as solidarity among its members. They were to pay collectively, ransom or blood money where the need arises. The Jewish tribes that were present in Madina at the time were also recognized by the Constitution as a community in itself which was part of the whole community forming the *Ummah* alongside the Muslims and other tribes. The Constitution regulates between the Jewish tribes and the Muslims, recognizing the religious freedom of the Jews as well as preserving their fundamental human rights. Any person that commits any atrocity will be held responsible individually irrespective of whether such person is a Muslim or a Jew or from any other tribe, unlike before where a whole tribe will be held responsible for a wrong committed by an individual member. The Constitution imposed the

18 Hashim, Y A 51.

19ibid 14

20 Hashim Y.A. 53.

duty of defending the State on the Jews alongside the believers and other tribes against any enemy. The Jews were not to make allies with any enemy of the believers nor engage in any war without the permission of the Prophet. All allies of the Jews will be treated in the same terms as with the Jews. The final arbitrator in any dispute should be the Prophet. From these, the position of the Prophet was very clear. The Constitution recognized the Prophethood of Prophet Muhammad and Madina regarded as a sacred city. The Prophet was regarded as the supreme judge, ruling in accordance with Islamic injunction. The Prophet has power to make decisions in matters of war and peace.²¹ Below is the full text of the Constitution:

9. TEXT OF THE CONSTITUTION

With the Name of God, the most beneficial, the All-merciful!

1. This is a prescript (*kitab*) of the Prophet Muhammad, (the Messenger of God) to operate among the Faithful Believers (*Mu'uminun*) and the Submissive to God, (*Muslimin*) from among the *Quraish* and (the people of) *Yathrib* and those who may be under them and join them, and take wars in their company.
2. Verily they constitute a political unit (*ummah*) as distinct from all the people (of the World).
3. The Emigrants from among the *Quraish* shall be (responsible) for their ward (*rub'ah*); and shall pay their blood-money in mutual collaboration, and shall secure the release of their prisoners by paying their ransom themselves, so that the mutual dealings between the Believers be in accordance with the principles of recognized goodness (*ma'ruf*) and justice.
4. And the *Banu 'Awl* shall be responsible for their own ward, and shall pay their blood-money in mutual collaboration as heretofore; and every group shall secure the release of its own prisoners by paying their ransom themselves, so that the dealings between the Believers be in accordance with the principles of recognized goodness and justice.
5. And the *Banu 'I-Harith* shall be responsible for their ward, and shall pay their blood-money in mutual collaboration as heretofore; and every group shall secure the release of its prisoners by paying their ransom themselves, so that the dealings between the Believers be in accordance with the principles of recognized goodness and justice.

²¹ *ibid* 55

6. And the *Banu Sa'idah* shall be responsible for their ward, and shall pay their blood-money in mutual collaboration as heretofore; and every group shall secure the release of its own prisoners by paying their ransom themselves, so that the dealings between the Believers be in accordance with the principles of recognized goodness and justice.

7. And the *Sams Jusham* shall be responsible for their ward, and shall pay their blood-money in mutual collaboration as heretofore; and every group shall secure the release of its own prisoners by paying their ransom themselves, so that the dealings between the Believers be in accordance with the principles of recognized goodness and justice.

8. And *Banun-Najjar* shall be responsible for their ward, and shall pay their blood-money in mutual collaboration as heretofore; and every group shall secure the release of its own prisoners by paying their ransom themselves, so that the dealings between the Believers be in accordance with the principles of recognized goodness and justice.

9. And the *Banu 'Amr ibn 'Awf* shall be responsible for their ward, and shall pay their blood-money in mutual collaboration as heretofore; and every group shall secure the release of its own prisoners by paying their ransom themselves, so that the dealings between the Believers be in accordance with the principles of recognized goodness and justice.

10. And the *Banun-Nabit* shall be responsible for their ward, and shall pay their blood-money in mutual collaboration as heretofore: and every group shall secure the release of its own prisoners by paying their ransom themselves, so that the dealings between the Believers be in accordance with the principles of recognized goodness and justice.

11. And *Banul-Aws* shall be responsible for their ward, and shall pay their blood-money in mutual collaboration as heretofore: and every group shall secure the release of its own prisoners by paying their ransom themselves, so that the dealings between the Believers be in accordance with the principles of recognized goodness and justice.

12. /a. And verily the Believers shall not leave any one hard pressed with debts without helping him in recognized goodness with regard to ransom or blood-money.

12. /b. And no Believer shall oppose the client of another Believer against him (i.e. this latter).

13. And verily the [hands of] pious believers should be raised against [every] such person as rises in rebellion or attempts to acquire anything by force, or is guilty of any violation of pledge

or excess or attempts to spread mischief among the Believers: and verily their hands shall rise all together against such a person, even if he be son of anyone of them.

14. And no Believer shall kill (*tagtulu*) another Believer in retaliation for an unbeliever (*kufir*), nor shall he help an unbeliever against a Believer.

15. And verily the protection (*dhimmah*) of God is one: and humblest of them (i.e., of the Believers) can, by extending his protection to anyone, put the obligation on all of them, and verily the Believers are brethren to one another as against all people (*of the world*).

16. And verily those who will obey us from among the Jews will have help and equality: neither shall they be oppressed nor shall any help be given against them.

17. And verily the peace of the Believers shall be one, [and] if there be any war in the path of God, no believer shall make any peace (with the enemy) apart from other Believers, unless it (i.e. this peace) be the same and equally binding on all.

18. And verily every detachment that will fight on our side will be relieved by turns.

19. And verily the Believers as a body shall take vengeance for each other of the bloodshed in the path of God.

20. /a. And undoubtedly the pious Believers are the followers of the best and the straightest guidance.

20. /b. And no polytheist (*mushrik* Arab subject) shall give any protection to property and to the life of any Quraishite, nor shall he come in the way of any Believer in this matter.

21. And verily if anyone intentionally murders a Believer and it is proved, he shall be killed in retaliation unless the heirs of the murdered person agree [to blood-money]; and verily all the Believers shall actually stand for this, and nothing else shall be lawful for them to do.

22. And verily it shall not be lawful for any Believer, who has accepted the contents of this document (*Sahifah*) and has faith in God and in the last day, to give help or protection to any murderer and verily whoever gives help or protection to such a person. God's curse and wrath shall be on him on the day of Resurrection, and no expense or compensation will be accepted from him (i.e. from the protector of the murderer to exonerate him).

23. And whenever ye differ about anything. its reference shall be to God and to Muhammad.

24. And verily the Jews shall bear (their) expenditure along with the Believers so long as they fight in conjunction.

25. And verily the Jews of the *Banu 'Awl'* shall be considered as a community (*ummah*) along with the Believers, for the Jews being their religion and for the Muslims their religion, be one client or original member of the tribe; but whosoever shall be guilty of oppression or violation (of treaty), shall put to trouble none but his own person and the members of his house (*ahl bait*).

26. And verily the Jews of the *Banu'n-Najjar* shall have the same rights as the Jews of the *Banu 'Awf*.

27. And verily the Jews of the *Banu'l-l.Iarith* shall have the same rights as the Jews of the *Banu 'Awf*.

28. And verily the Jews of the *Banu Sa'idah* shall have the same rights as the Jews of the *Banu 'Awf*.

29. And verily the Jews of the *Banu Jusham* shall have the same rights as the Jews of the *Banu 'Awl'*.

30. And verily the Jews of the *Banu'l-Aws* shall have the same rights as the Jews of the *Banu 'Awf*.

31. And verily the Jews of the *Banu 'ha' labah* shall have the same rights as the Jews of the *Banu 'Awf*; but whosoever shall be guilty of oppression and violation of the treaty shall put to trouble none but his own person and the members of his house.

32. And verily the *jafnah* is a branch of the (tribe of) *Tha'lahah*, even like them.

33. And verily the *Banu'sh-Shutaibah* shall have the same rights as the Jews of the *Banu 'Awf*: and verily there shall be fulfillment and not violation.

34. And verily the clients of the *Tha'lahah* shall have the same rights as the original members.

35. And verily the sub-branches (*hitunah*) of the Jews shall have the same rights as the principal members.

36. /a. and verily none of them shall go out (on a military expedition) except with the permission of Muhammad.

36/b. And verily no obstruction shall be placed in the way of (anyone's) retaliation of a wound; and whosoever sheds blood shall be personally responsible for it even as the members of his house, or else (i.e. to do otherwise) it will be injustice: and verily God is along with those who observe this most scrupulously.

37. /a. And verily the Jews shall bear their expenses (of war) and the Muslims shall bear their expenses; and verily there shall be aid between them as against those who fight the parties (*ahl*) to this document (*yahifuh*). And there shall be sincere counsel and well-wishing between them: and there shall be fulfillment (of pledge) and not violation.

37./b. And verily no one shall violate the pledge of his ally (*hair*); and verily help shall be given in favour of the oppressed.

38. And verily the Jews shall bear (their) expenditure along with the Believers so long as they fight in conjunction,

39. And verily the valley (*jawf*) of *Yathrib* shall constitute an inviolable territory for the parties to this document.

40. And verily the protected person (*Jar*) shall he considered just like the original member (who has given protection); neither shall he (the protected person) be harmed, nor shall he himself violate the pledge.

41. And verily no refuge will be given (by the protected person to others) without the permission of the original people of the place.

42. And verily if any murder or quarrel takes between the parties to this document (*sahifah*), from which any trouble may be feared, it shall be referred to God and to Muhammad, Messenger of God, may God bless him and protect; and verily God is the guarantee of the most faithful and scrupulous observance of the contents of this document.

43. And verily the *Quraish* shall be given no protection or those who help them.

44. And verily there shall be aid between them (the Muslims and the Jews) against those who invade *Yathrib*.

45. Ia. And if they (*the Jews*) are invited to peace to participate in and to adhere to it, they shall participate in and adhere to it; and verily if they invite likewise, the same shall be incumbent upon the Believers in their favour, excepting one who fights for the cause of religion.

45./b. On every group shall rest the responsibility for the part [of the city] which faces them.

46. And the Jews of *al-Aws* clients as well as original members, shall have the same rights as the parties to this document (*sahifah*), with the purest fulfillment with regard to the parties to this document; and verily there shall be fulfillment and not violation; no evil-doer earns anything except against his own self; and verily God is the guarantee of the most trustful and most scrupulous observance of the contents of this document.

47. And verily this prescript (*kitab*) shall not protect any oppressor or violator of pledge; and verily whoever goes out (on a military expedition) shall have security, and whoever stays in Madina shall have security, except on who commits oppression and violation of the pledge; and verily God is the protector of those who fulfill and observe the pledge scrupulously, even as Muhammad. Messenger of God—may God bless and protect him—is (the protector)."²²

10. THE CONSTITUTIONAL PRINCIPLES/FEATURES OF A MODERN CONSTITUTION

Various countries of the modern world are guided by a single document referred to as a constitution. Those without a single document as a Constitution still claimed to have an unwritten one. Thus, Countries without a Constitution are frowned at and regarded as undemocratic and backward. A modern Constitution is referred to as a rationalist exercise, where people agreed on the terms of government. It required a single document, antecedent to government that provided a comprehensive fundamental law.²³ All such Constitutions have common principles/features such as sovereignty, arms of government (executive, legislative and judicial arm), freedom of religion, right to life, citizenship, rights and duties of a citizen, territorial jurisdiction as well as concept of equality etc.

11. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE CONSTITUTIONAL PRINCIPLES IN SAHIFAT AL-MADINA

- i. Sovereignty;** Sovereignty in the *Sahifat al-Madina* belonged to Allah. Meaning that the highest authority must come from Allah in decision making. Even though there is

²²Parvaze Ahmad Bhat, 126

²³Available @ www.academic.oup.com accessed on 9 July 2024

room for human reasoning in Islamic law (*ijtihad*), it must be in light of the *Qur'an* and *Sunna*. There are many articles in *Sahifat al-Madina* that covered the sovereignty of Allah; The preamble; in the name of Allah, the Beneficent, the Merciful. **Article 23 provides**; when a matter is disputed, it must be referred to Allah and Muhammad. **Article 42 provides**; if any dispute or controversy likely to cause trouble among the people of this document should arise, it must be referred to Allah and to Muhammad, the messenger of Allah. **Article 47 provides**; ...Allah is the protector of the good and the God-fearing and Muhammad is the messenger of Allah²⁴

- ii. Territorial Jurisdiction of the State**; every sovereign state must have a defined boundaries as its territorial jurisdiction set out in its constitution. Many articles in the *Sahifat al-Madina* stated that *Yathrib* (another name for Madina) was the state where the constitution was to be applied. **Article 1 provides**; this is a document from Muhammad the Prophet, the messenger of Allah peace be upon him, governing the relations between the believers and Muslims of the *Quraish* and *Yathrib Madina* and those who followed them and joined them and labored with them. **Article 36 (a) provides**; none of them shall go out of *Madina* except with the permission of Muhammad. **Article 39**; *Yathrib* shall be a sanctuary for the people of this document. **Article 44**; the contracting parties are bound to help one another against any attack on *Yathrib*. **Article 47**; this document will not protect the unjust and the sinner. The man who goes forth to fight and the man who stays at home at *Madina* are safe...²⁵
- iii. Arms of Government**; most of the constitutions of a democratically elected government define who are the Legislature responsible for law making, the Executive who are to implement the law and the Judiciary whose duty is to interpret the law. **Article 1 provides**; this is a document from Muhammad, here the Prophet was the legislature, the law comes from him. **Article 36 stated that**; “none of them shall go out of Madina except with the permission of Muhammad” this is an executive element in the document. **Article 23 & 42 provides**; “when there is a dispute, it must be referred to Allah and Muhammad” i.e. for adjudications.
- iv. Citizenship**: Another important principle in a constitution is a provision on who is a citizen of the country the constitution is regulating. In *Sahifat al-Madina*, Citizenship

24 Zaid Mohamed 22

25 ibid

was covered by many articles, stating clearly who was a citizen. **Article 1**; this is a document... Muslims of the Quraish and Yathrib Madina and those who followed them and joined them and labored with them. **Article 2**; they are one Ummah to the exclusion of all men. **Article 3**; the Quraish emigrants according to their... **Article 4**; the (tribe of) Banu 'Awf according to their.... **Article 5**; the Banu al- Harith Ibn Al-Khazraj according to their.... **Article 6**; And Banu Saa'idah according to their.... **Article 7**; And Banu Jasham according to their **Article 8**; the Banu al-Najjar according to their **Article 9**; the Banu 'Amr Ibn 'Awf according to their **Article 10**; the Banu al-Nabit according to their.... **Article 11**; the Banu al-Aus according to their present custom.... **Article 16**; to the Jew who follows us belongs help..... **Article 25**; the Jews of Banu 'Awf are one community with the believers.... **Article 26**; the same applies to the Jews of the Banu al-Najjar **Article 27**; the same applies to the Jews of the Banu al-Harith as applies to the Jews of Banu 'Awf **Article 28**; the same applies to the Jews of the Banu Sa'ida as applies to the Jews of the Banu 'Awf **Article 29**; the same applies to the Jews of the Banu Jusham as applies to the Jews of Banu 'Awf **Article 30**; the same applies to the Jews of Banu Tha'laba except those who behave unjustly and sinfully, for they injure only themselves and their families **Article 31**; the same applies to the Jews of the Banu Aus as applies to the Jews of the Banu 'Awf **Article 32**; And the Jafna, a clan of the Tha'labah are as themselves. **Article 33**; the same applies to the Banu al-Shutaybah as applies to the Jews of Banu 'Awf. Loyalty is a protection against treachery. **Article 34**; the freedmen of Tha'laba are as themselves. **Article 35**; the close friends of the Jews are as themselves.

- v. **Rights and Duties of the Citizens**; Constitutions basically set out rights and duties of its citizens, in *Sahifat al-Madina*, Article 16 and 25 are on the rights of a citizen; **Article 16**; to the Jew who follow us belongs help and equality. He shall not be wronged nor shall his enemies be aided. **Article 25**; the Jews of the Banu 'Awf are one Community with the believers (the Jews have their religion and the Muslims have theirs, they and their freed men, except those who behave unjustly and sinfully, for they injure only themselves and their families. The duties of the citizens is provided for under articles 1 to 23 with regard to the Muslims and article 24 to 42 outline the rights and duties of the non-Muslims that is the Jews and their friends who were not Jews.

- vi. **Freedom of Religion:** Another important element of a Constitution is the provision of freedom of religion to its citizens. In *Sahifat al-Madina* freedom of religion is for the non-Muslims, they don't have to become Muslims to live in Madina. The non-Muslims can change their religion to any other religion. However, this right is exclusive to the non-Muslims, for a Muslim it is considered as treasonable felony. Freedom of religion is provided for under the following articles in *Sahifat al-Madina*: **Article 25:** the Jews of the Banu 'Awf are one community with the believers (the Jews have their religion and the Muslims have theirs)... **Article 1, 2:** those who followed them and joined them and labored with them.... **Article 16:** to the Jew who follows us belongs help and equality. He shall not be wronged nor shall his enemies be aided.

- vii. **Concept of Equality:** Another important principle of a constitution is the sense of equality among the citizens. Every citizen should be treated equally. Under *Sahifat al-Madina* all citizens are equal. This means they have equal rights and equal duties. The citizenship is one. This can be seen under the following articles: **Article 16:** to the Jew who follows us belongs help and equality. He shall not be wronged nor shall his enemies be aided. **Article 25:** the Jews of the Banu 'Awf are one community with the believers (the Jews have their religion and the Muslims have theirs).....

- viii. **Concept of Responsibility:** Sense of responsibility is crucial in achieving equality in a society. In *Sahifat al-Madina* responsibility is individualistic, that is everyone is responsible for his act. This principle was introduced by the Prophet as the situation was opposite before Islam. Before, any crime committed by a member of a clan (tribe), the whole clan must take responsibility. The Prophet abolished this system and declared that everyone must bear the consequences of his own action. **Article 37(b):** A man is not liable for his ally's misdeeds...²⁶

12. CONCLUSION

From the above discussion with facts and evidences, it is clear that politics is deeply rooted in Islam. It is even clearer that without political leadership, the religion will never achieve its desired goal. For this reason, it was the Prophet who first established the Islamic City-State which was later converted into a Confederate with the conquest of other settlements under the umbrella of the Islamic State of Madina. Abubakar the first Caliph after the Prophet continued

²⁶ Zaid Mohamed 24

with the expansion of the Islamic State and consolidated the political structure of the Islamic System of Governance. The overview of the content of Sahifat al-Madina clearly shows that all the modern constitutional principles are present in the content of Sahifat. Although it may not be titled as such, Sahifat al-Madina can only be regarded as a Constitution and nothing else.